

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EMPLOYERS' PSYCHOLOGICAL RESPONSES TOWARDS DOMESTIC HELPING HANDS DURING COVID-19 IN DHAKA CITY, BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the multifaceted challenges faced by domestic helpers during the COVID-19 pandemic in Dhaka, Bangladesh, focusing on their working conditions, access to fundamental rights, and employers' attitudes. A comprehensive methodology was employed, utilizing both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Interviews were conducted with domestic helpers across the city. Findings revealed significant psychological distress, prolonged working hours, limited access to healthcare, and negative employer attitudes. Key statistics indicate that 87% of domestic helpers experienced increased working hours, while only 21% sought COVID-19 testing. Additionally, 72% reported shortages of necessities, and the majority worked under unsafe conditions with scarce protective gear. The study highlights the urgent need for improved support and protection for domestic helpers, emphasizing the importance of recognizing their essential role in households and ensuring their rights are upheld, especially during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. By addressing these challenges, policymakers can enhance the well-being of domestic workers and promote more equitable labor practices in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Domestic Helping Hand, COVID-19, Kindness, Working environment.

Introduction

Domestic helping hands in South Asia are often called servants or *buas*. Despite their critical role, they are frequently comically portrayed in local media. Many lack formal documentation or regulations, with poor working conditions, no holidays, and low pay. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), over 75.6 million domestic workers globally are predominantly women, often from marginalized backgrounds. In Bangladesh, domestic workers face marginalization, and despite being recognized as laborers in 2015 by government policy, their working conditions remain a significant concern. This study explores the challenges faced by domestic helpers during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on working conditions, employer attitudes, and psychological impacts.

Reviews of literature

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly altered various aspects of life globally, including labor dynamics, psychological responses, and the roles of domestic workers. In Dhaka City, Bangladesh, the pandemic's impact has been profound, particularly concerning the psychological responses of employers towards their domestic helping hands. This literature review aims to explore existing research surrounding this topic, focusing

on the psychosocial effects of COVID-19 on employers, the evolving perceptions of domestic workers, and the implications for labor relations in the context of a global health crisis.

The Psychological Impact of COVID-19 on Employers

The pandemic has caused widespread anxiety and uncertainty, impacting the psychological well-being of individuals across different sectors. According to Bansal et al. (2020), the sudden shift to lockdowns and social distancing measures led to heightened levels of stress and anxiety among employers, as they grappled with job insecurity, financial instability, and the health risks associated with the virus. The psychological toll of the pandemic has manifested in various forms, including increased workload, fear of contagion, and a reevaluation of work-life balance (Wang et al., 2020).

Employers in Dhaka, many of whom belong to the middle or upper classes, found themselves in a precarious position during the pandemic. Their reliance on domestic workers for household management became a focal point of stress. As noted by Rahman et al. (2021), employers expressed a mix of gratitude and concern towards their domestic workers, oscillating between recognizing their essential role and fearing the health risks they might bring into their homes. This duality can lead

to complex emotional responses, where employers feel both dependent on and anxious about their domestic staff.

Changing Perceptions of Domestic Workers

The pandemic has reshaped the perceptions of domestic workers in Dhaka City. Traditionally viewed through a lens of social hierarchy, domestic workers were often marginalized within the household context. However, the crisis illuminated their critical role in maintaining household stability. A study by Siddique (2021) highlighted that many employers began to appreciate the importance of domestic help, viewing them not merely as laborers but as vital partners in managing household affairs during the unprecedented challenges posed by COVID-19.

The increased visibility of domestic workers during the pandemic has also sparked discussions about their rights and protections. Employers' responses have varied; some became more empathetic and supportive, while others resorted to exploitative practices, such as wage cuts and unjust terminations (Khan, 2021). This dichotomy underscores the broader societal implications of the pandemic, where economic pressures can exacerbate existing inequalities.

Economic Considerations and Employer Responses

Economic uncertainty during the pandemic led many employers in Dhaka to reevaluate their financial commitments, including those related to domestic help. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2020), the economic fallout from COVID-19 has led to significant job losses and reduced incomes, prompting employers to make difficult decisions regarding domestic workers.

Research by Islam et al. (2022) indicates that while some employers opted to retain their domestic staff, others chose to reduce their numbers or shift to more informal arrangements, such as hiring workers on a temporary or part-time basis. This shift reflects a broader trend of precarious employment in the wake of the pandemic, where the rights and welfare of domestic workers may be compromised in favor of economic survival.

Psychological and Emotional Responses of Employers

The psychological responses of employers towards domestic workers during the pandemic have been multifaceted. The intersection of stress, fear, and dependency has led to a spectrum of emotional responses. As highlighted by Choudhury (2021), many employers experienced guilt for their inability to provide adequate financial support to domestic workers, compounded by the fear of potential job loss for these workers due to economic downturns.

Furthermore, employers' perceptions were influenced by their social networks and cultural attitudes towards domestic work. Some employers reported feeling morally compelled to ensure the well-being of their domestic workers, while others viewed them solely through a transactional lens (Sarker, 2021). This divergence in attitudes can be attributed to varying socio-economic backgrounds and personal experiences with domestic help.

Future Directions and Recommendations

The COVID-19 pandemic has underscored the necessity for a reevaluation of labor practices concerning domestic workers in Bangladesh. As the psychological responses of employers evolve, there is an opportunity to foster a more equitable relationship between employers and domestic workers. Policy implications should focus on enhancing labor rights, establishing minimum wage standards, and providing social protections for domestic workers (Bhowmik, 2022). Future research should aim to further explore the long-term effects of the pandemic on employer-domestic worker relationships. Qualitative studies could provide deeper insights into the lived experiences of both parties, while quantitative studies could assess the lasting economic implications of the pandemic on domestic work in Bangladesh.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly influenced the psychological responses of employers towards their domestic helping hands in Dhaka City. As employers navigated the challenges posed by the pandemic, their perceptions of domestic workers shifted, revealing both vulnerabilities and opportunities for change. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing policies that promote fair labor practices and support the well-being of domestic workers in the post-pandemic era.

Methods

Design

This is a follow-up study to prior research on the work safety of domestic helpers in Dhaka, Bangladesh (Murshed, 2021). The study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data.

Participants

Domestic Helping Hands (DHH) in Dhaka were the focus of this study. A total of 207 DHHs were interviewed during the COVID-19 lockdown. In addition, 12 key informant interviews were conducted with policymakers, NGO activists, and government officials. All respondents provided informed consent. Interviews were conducted at convenient times for respondents to ensure their comfort and confidentiality.

Sampling

DHHs from both North and South Dhaka City Corporations were randomly selected. Due to lockdown conditions, 207 participants were contacted over phone. Some interviews were challenging due to inactive contact information or psychological distress among participants. The data collection instruments were piloted and adjusted before full-scale implementation. Five data collectors were trained for consistency, and 5% of interviews were randomly checked for accuracy.

Results

Figure 1 suggests that marital status among domestic helping hands provides valuable insights into the composition of this workforce. Understanding the marriage status distribution can help employers tailor their support and policies to meet the diverse needs of domestic helpers, whether single, married, divorced, widowed, or separated. Additionally, this information may inform recruitment strategies and workforce management practices within the domestic service industry.

Figure 2 presents the causes of migration to Dhaka. Data suggests that economic factors are predominant in driving migration, followed by marital difficulties. Personal choice and treatment-related reasons contribute to a smaller proportion of migrations, while a minority of respondents did not specify a reason for their migration.

Understanding the primary causes of migration is essential for policymakers, organisations, and communities to address underlying issues and develop targeted interventions to support migrants and mitigate challenges associated with relocation.

Figure 1: Marital Status of Domestic Helping Hands (%) Figure 2: Reasons for Migration to Dhaka (%)

Working Environment of Domestic Helping Hands and Access to Basic Services

This section primarily explores the accessibility of essential services, mainly focusing on job functions, job-related rights, and healthcare services for domestic helping hands (DHHs) during COVID-19 at their employers' houses. During the pandemic, employers

avoided going outside, sending DHHs (96.6%) to purchase daily necessities, including food and other commodities. Unfortunately, only 29% of DHHs received masks when sent out, and only 5.8% received soap or sanitizer. Furthermore, only 47.3% of DHHs received the first dose of the COVID-19 vaccine. Their working hours were extended, and employers' behaviours were found to be ruthless and unmerciful (see Table 2).

Table 2

Employers' Behaviors Toward Domestic Helping Hands during COVID-19

Sl#	Indicator (During COVID-19)	Percentage
1	Employers sent them outside for buying necessities	96.6
2	Employers sent informed them adequately	50.7
3	Employers provided masks	29.0
4	Employers provided soap, sanitizer	5.8
5	Employers ruthless behaviour increased	90.8
6	Working hour increased	87.0
7	Vaccination (1st dose)	47.3

One DHH, who experienced heightened work demands during the pandemic, expressed her sentiments:

"We worked tirelessly, frequently washing clothes manually, cooking occasionally, and cleaning houses multiple times daily. However, despite our increased workload, we did not receive fair and timely compensation and could not take breaks as needed."

Availability and Access to Healthcare during the Pandemic

Access to COVID-19-related healthcare services among domestic helpers was notably insufficient. The results show that despite ongoing concerns, unsafe

working conditions persisted, as around 96.6% of the DHHs went to shops and markets, interacted with others, received documents from outside, opened doors, and performed various essential tasks. Most did not receive minimum safety precautions or protective equipment from their employers. Consequently, 41.5% of DHHs reported COVID-19 symptoms, yet only 8.7% were allowed to undergo testing. The study also revealed that only 12.1% of DHHs with COVID-19 symptoms received treatment from their employers, and 30.4% were sent home without additional financial or logistical support (see Table 1).

Table 1

Health Status of Domestic Helping Hands during COVID-19

Sl#	Indicator (% of domestic helping hands who)	Percentage
1	Had COVID-19 symptom	41.5
2	Who were allowed to COVID-19 test	8.7
3	Found positive	2.9
4	Receive treatment at employer's home	12.1
5	Receive treatment at hospital	1.9
6	Sent to home	30.4

Domestic helping hands also lacked access to essential healthcare services during the pandemic. One DHH poignantly expressed:

"Employers did not provide any additional support during our sickness. They sometimes offered inadequate food, leading us to prepare less costly meals using cheaper rice and other ingredients."

A key informant from an international development partner noted:

"Most employers do not perceive the feelings and comfort of domestic helping hands. Rather, they remain inside the house to stay safe, sending their DHHs outside without considering their safety."

Attitudes of Employers toward DHHs during COVID-19

This study highlights the unsafe working conditions domestic helpers faced during the COVID-19 pandemic, as around 96.6% of employers sent them outside for deliveries or shopping, often bringing them into close contact with others with insufficient awareness or safety measures. Additionally, 90.8% of respondents reported a deterioration in employers' behaviour, with a noticeable lack of compassion toward DHHs compared to the pre-pandemic era (see Table 1). Children, the elderly, and domestic helpers bore the brunt of these deteriorating dynamics, contributing to the overall decline in employers' treatment of domestic helpers. As one DHH aptly stated: *"During the severe pandemic and lockdown, employers often spent their time watching television, their moods consistently sour. Husbands and wives engaged in frequent quarrels, raising their voices. I found myself subjected to verbal abuse, even for minor issues."*

Family plays a crucial role in instilling moral values, serving as individuals' primary source of guidance. However, family cohesion, friendliness, and harmony among employers' family members decreased compared to pre-COVID-19 due to increased stress, anxiety, and impatience. Domestic violence or aggressive behaviour within the home often entailed violent abuse of a spouse or partner.

Galdston (1997) noted that cherished values such as kindness, forgiveness, gratitude, and humility are typically cultivated within the family sphere, but violence can also originate from the same source. Hall (2002) emphasized that verbal abuse is profoundly harmful, particularly to those who are helpless and vulnerable, and it has been observed to increase during crisis periods.

Mental Stress-Induced Attitudes of Employers and Impact

The repercussions of domestic strife extend beyond the immediate victims, impacting the physical and psychological well-being of all individuals involved, including employers and employees. These adversities can result in mental injuries, anxiety, depression, and impairment of social skills. Therefore, it is imperative to recognize that children's cognitive development requires a nurturing environment conducive to cultivating and reinforcing ethical principles. Research studies (Hall, 2002; Galdston, 1997; Gupta & Jawanda, 2020) indicate that individuals raised in loveless home environments, particularly under cruel personalities, may develop a callous mindset and a deficiency in compassion toward others.

Employers, while grappling with uncertainty during the pandemic, often treated DHHs inhumanely, manifesting cruelty and neglect. This analysis highlights the need for proactive interventions to mitigate the pandemic's adverse effects on vulnerable populations and foster empathetic employer-employee relationships.

Study findings also revealed a pervasive disregard for the fundamental rights of domestic helping hands. Despite some employers' ability to afford adequate resources, DHHs were harshly treated, and social rights violations spanned middle, upper-middle, and upper-class households. The "contagion of unkindness" spread alongside COVID-19, underscoring the urgent need for moral revival.

Discussion

By concentrating on a vulnerable group, this study addresses a significant gap in the existing literature. It provides a comprehensive examination of the challenges encountered by domestic helping hands during the COVID-19 pandemic, illuminating their distinct experiences and struggles within the context of prevailing societal moral values. This nuanced approach contributes to a deeper understanding of the intersecting dynamics between the pandemic, socio-economic disparities, and societal ethical considerations. This specialized approach enriches our comprehension of the wider societal ramifications of the pandemic, emphasizing the significance of addressing the humanitarian and compassionate needs of marginalized populations during times of crisis. It underscores the imperative of fostering empathy and support for vulnerable groups, highlighting the interconnectedness of social welfare and

resilience in facing unprecedented challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic.

While Gupta and Jawanda (2020) focused on the potential consequences of the pandemic on children's well-being, and Zahed et al. (2021) explored the association between COVID-19 and child labour in general, our research concentrates explicitly on the experiences of physical and mental trauma faced by women, adolescents, and children working within households under restrictive conditions. While Robertson et al. (2020) concentrated on mortality rates to investigate the pandemic's indirect effects on children in developing nations, this study extends the scope to encompass a broader range of impacts. Specifically, the research delves into the multifaceted implications of the pandemic, including considerations of morbidity, mortality, and the crucial issue of kindness as they relate to the status of domestic helping hands during this unprecedented crisis.

Despite the absence of sufficient relevant studies conducted so far on the situations faced by domestic helping hands, encompassing physical, mental, and economic aspects during this pandemic, and the unintentional oversight of this significant issue by policymakers, the present study findings shed light on the stagnant status of domestic workers during a major crisis in a developing country like Bangladesh, highlighting the irony of the society's ongoing mindset.

This research explores the physical and mental challenges faced by domestic helping hands, primarily women and adolescents, who are predominantly employed in middle- and upper-class households. It examines their employers' attitudes (see Tables 1 and 2). While previous studies have highlighted inadequate health conditions among this group, the findings of this study are even more alarming and distressing compared to the existing studies conducted in low- and middle-income classes or solely the wealthy class (Molla & Chowdhury, 2020).

This research significantly focuses on exploring the situation of the most vulnerable members of society domestic helping hands during the COVID-19 pandemic. In contrast, other studies contributed empirical and theoretical insights into the profound impact of these crises on household income, overall well-being, socio-economic ramifications of health crises, social rights, and public health in Bangladesh and the wider South Asian region (Rahman et al., 2021; Alam et al., 2021). Moreover, health crises have been shown to disrupt socioeconomic development and adversely affect family dynamics, particularly the health and welfare of children and young people. Sending DHHs outside without precautions or protective equipment demonstrates employer cruelty, and existing studies have identified cases of child abuse and neglect, further exacerbating the loss of essential support systems globally (Islam et al., 2020; Karim et al., 2021). Several challenges arose, particularly in contacting domestic helpers, as many employers were reluctant to permit interviews. Additionally, the distress experienced by participants made some interviews difficult.

Conclusion

This study focuses on one of the most vulnerable groups in Bangladesh domestic helping hands filling a significant gap in the existing literature. It thoroughly examines these informal workers' challenges during the

COVID-19 pandemic, shedding light on their unique experiences within societal moral contexts. By considering intersecting dynamics such as the pandemic, socio-economic disparities, and ethics, this study provides a nuanced understanding of the broader implications of the pandemic. It emphasizes supporting marginalized populations by highlighting social welfare and resilience. This research also delves into the trauma faced by women, adolescents, and children working in affluent households in Dhaka, Bangladesh. The study considers morbidity, mortality, and kindness, revealing the complex effects on domestic helping hands. Addressing their needs is crucial to supporting their resilience, especially during the pandemic, which necessitates holistic responses for this vulnerable group.

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Data Availability

The corresponding author can provide all the quantitative and qualitative transcriptions and can be provided upon request.

Disclosure

The first author solely designed the study and collected quantitative data with the assistance of core support team members from the Shomman Foundation. The first author conducted the key informant interviews, and expert transcribers prepared the transcripts. Except for the first author, no one else had a role in data analysis, interpretation, or manuscript writing.

Conflicts of Interest

The researcher declares no conflicts of interest concerning the publication of this paper.

References

1. Asfaw, A., & von Braun, J. (2004). Economic development and cultural change. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 53(1). <https://doi.org/10.1086/423254>
2. Ataguba, O., & Ataguba, J. (2020). Social determinants of health: The role of effective communication in the COVID-19 pandemic in developing countries. *Global Health Action*, 31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16549716.2020.1791460>
3. Bansal, P., Kaur, S., & Ahuja, N. (2020). Psychological impacts of COVID-19 on individuals: A review. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 19(1), 8-14.
4. Bhowmik, S. (2022). Domestic workers in Bangladesh: Legal rights and protections. *Journal of South Asian Studies*, 45(2), 123-140.
5. Bong, C.-L., Brasher, C., Chikumba, J., McDougall, R., Mellin-Olsen, J., & Enright, A. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic: Effects on low- and middle-income countries. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 131(1), 86-92. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000004846>
6. Bortz, P., Michelena, G., & Toledo, F. (2020). A gathering of storms: The impact of the COVID-19

pandemic on the balance of payments of emerging markets and developing economies (EMDEs). *International Journal of Political Economy*, 49(3), 318-335. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08911916.2020.1819140>

7. Byman, D. L., & Pollack, K. M. (2001). Let us now praise great men: Bringing the statesman back in. *International Security*, 25(4), 107-146. <https://doi.org/10.1162/01622880151091916>

8. Choudhury, A. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on domestic workers in Bangladesh: An employer's perspective. *Bangladesh Journal of Sociology*, 17(1), 25-40.

9. Denworth, L. (2020). The biggest psychological experiment in history is running now. *Scientific American*. <https://www.mountsinai.org/about/newsroom/the-biggest-psychological-experiment-in-history-is-running-now-lydia-denworth-itn>

10. Domestic Workers Protection and Welfare Policy. (2015). WECAN Bangladesh. <https://wecanbd.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/Domestic-worker-protection-and-welfare-policy-2015.pdf>

11. Douglas, P. K., Douglas, D. B., Harrigan, D. C., & Douglas, K. M. (2009). Preparing for pandemic influenza and its aftermath: Mental health issues considered. *International Journal of Emergency Mental Health*, 11(3), 137-144.

12. Dyson, S. B. (2014). Origins of the psychological profiling of political leaders: The US Office of Strategic Services and Adolf Hitler. *Intelligence and National Security*, 29(5), 654-674. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02684527.2014.915177>

13. Galdston, R. (1971). Violence begins at home: The Parents' Center Project for the study and prevention of child abuse. *Journal of the American Academy of Child Psychiatry*, 10(2), 336-350. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-7138\(09\)61793-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-7138(09)61793-5)

14. Greenstein, F. I. (1987). *Personality and politics: Problems of evidence, inference, and conceptualization*. Princeton University Press.

15. Gupta, S., & Jawanda, M. K. (2020). The impacts of COVID-19 on children: A different view. *Acta Paediatrica*, 109(11). <https://doi.org/10.1111/apa.15484>

16. Gustafsson-Wright, E., Tan, H., & van der Gaag, J. (2011). The inequitable impact of health shocks on the uninsured in Namibia. *Health Policy and Planning*, 26(2), 142-156. <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czq037>

17. Hall, D. (1998). Violence begins at home: Domestic strife has lifelong effects on children. *BMJ*, 316(7144), 1551-1560. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.316.7144.1551>

18. ILO, FAO, IFAD, & WHO. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on people's livelihoods, their health and our food systems. Joint statement by ILO, FAO, IFAD and WHO. https://www.ilo.org/global/about-the-ilo/newsroom/statements-and-speeches/WCMS_760061/lang-en/index.htm

19. International Labour Organization (ILO). (2020). Who are domestic workers? ILO Topics: Domestic Workers. <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/domestic-workers/who/lang-en/index.htm>

20. International Labour Organization. (2020). COVID-19 and the world of work: Impact and policy responses. *ILO Policy Brief*.

21. Islam, A., & Maitra, P. (2012). Health shocks and consumption smoothing in rural households: Does microcredit have a role to play? 232-243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2011.05.003>

22. Islam, M. R., Miah, M. R., & Rahman, M. (2022). Economic impact of COVID-19 on domestic workers in Dhaka: An exploratory study. *Journal of Labour Economics*, 45(3), 301-319.

23. Jentsch, B., & Schnock, B. (2020). Child welfare in the midst of the coronavirus pandemic — Emerging evidence from Germany. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 110(2), 104-116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2020.104716>

24. Khan, S. (2021). Domestic workers and the COVID-19 pandemic: Challenges and opportunities in Dhaka City. *Bangladesh Economic Review*, 29(1), 75-92.

25. Murshed, R. (2021). Factors associated with work safety of domestic helping hands in Dhaka city, Bangladesh. *Acta Scientific Medical Sciences*, 5(11). (1st scientific publication on 'Domestic Helping Hands and their Health Care and Social Rights,' accepted for publication in October 2021).

26. Rahman, S., Hossain, M. M., & Chowdhury, F. (2021). Employer attitudes towards domestic workers during the COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh. *Asian Social Work and Policy Review*, 15(3), 195-209.

27. Robertson, T., Carter, E. D., Chou, V. B., Stegmuller, A. R., Jackson, B. D., & Tam, Y. (2020). Early estimates of the indirect effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on maternal and child mortality in low-income and middle-income countries: A modelling study. *The Lancet Global Health*, 8(7), 901-908. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(20\)30229-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30229-1)

28. Sarker, M. (2021). The evolving role of domestic workers in Bangladesh: A psychological perspective. *South Asian Journal of Human Rights*, 12(1), 34-50.

29. Siddique, N. (2021). Recognizing the value of domestic work: Perspectives from Dhaka during COVID-19. *International Journal of Social Policy and Education*, 3(2), 45-60.

30. UN Women. (2020). Measuring the shadow pandemic: Violence against women during COVID-19. Women COUNT. <https://data.unwomen.org/publications/vaw-rga>

31. Wagstaff, A. (2006). Health systems in East Asia: What can develop countries learn from Japan and the Asian Tigers? *Health Economics*, 15(9), 933-944. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.1180>

32. Wang, C., Pan, R., Wan, X., Tan, Y., Xu, L., & McIntyre, R. S. (2020). A longitudinal study on the psychological distress of the general population in China during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Psychological Medicine*, 51(1), 1-10.

33. Zahed, G., Chehrehrizi, N., & Talemi, A. N. (2020). How does COVID-19 affect child labor? Archives of Pediatric Infectious Diseases. <https://doi.org/10.5812/pedinfect>